

SOCIALRES PROJECT – FOSTERING SOCIALLY INNOVATIVE AND INCLUSIVE STRATEGIES FOR EMPOWERING CITIZENS IN THE RENEWABLE ENERGY MARKET OF THE FUTURE

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ABSTRACT: SocialRES aims to devise effective ways of increasing social innovation leading to greater social acceptability of renewable energy systems. This is done by a better understanding of support structures for successful social innovations in the renewable energy sector such as Renewable Energy Cooperatives, Aggregators and Crowdfunding Platforms. These businesses facilitate consumers to take an active role in the electricity system. Through research excellence and co-creation of knowledge, SocialRES will develop socially innovative and inclusive strategies for the energy system of the future. SocialRES will supplement the existing fragmented data on social innovations with new understandings from businesses, end-users and stakeholders to provide a comprehensive evidence base for policy design. Innovative techniques will be employed such as a Peer to Peer (P2P) crowd-investing for renewable energy sources projects, P2P lending and *P2P virtual photovoltaic electricity platform* for aggregators. The innovative P2P photovoltaic virtual platform will be developed as a pilot software application in off-line mode and will facilitate the understanding about existing barriers within current electricity markets and policies. Experience will therefore be accumulated related to the main issues with the common access for energy trades between different actors on the market: prosumers, consumers, balancing responsible party and distributed photovoltaic generators.

Keywords: Social innovation, Crowdfunding, Aggregation, Cooperatives

1 AIM AND APPROACH

Social innovation is an essential facilitator of energy democracy but increasing social innovation must be mindful of the wider context of increased urbanisation, migration and economic polarisation and a shifting technological, data and privacy management landscape. These wider challenges will bring significant changes in the way citizens engage with the industry in the future and require careful consideration to avoid a situation where the low-carbon energy scenario and increase in social innovation advances contribute to further social inequalities. By addressing the mentioned challenges, SocialRES will devise more effective ways of increasing social innovation, leading to greater social acceptability as well as more durable governance arrangements and socioeconomic benefits.

The overall ambition of SocialRES is to close non-technological research gaps that impede the widespread uptake of social innovation business and service models in the European energy sector. Social innovations are defined “as new ideas (products, services and models) that simultaneously meet social needs (more effectively than

alternatives) and create new social relationships or collaborations. In other words, they are innovations that are not only good for society but also enhance society’s capacity to act“ [1].

SocialRES identifies the business models and services implemented by Cooperatives, Crowdfunders and Aggregators, operating in the Renewable Energy sector, as the social innovations to be investigated. By creating a better understanding of socio-economic, socio-cultural, socio-political and gender factors, a more evidence-based regulatory, investment and policy landscape will be enabled for decision makers. This creates the essential environment for clean energy business and service models, which place *consumers at centre stage in the energy system*.

The partners involved in the SocialRES project have been carefully selected in order to ensure the achievement of the project objectives and to maximise the scope of research and innovation involvement of the target group and key actors. The project’s target group consists of providers of socially innovative business models and services such as crowdfunding platforms, cooperatives and aggregators, all of which have been directly involved in the SocialRES consortium as partners.

The SocialRES consortium brings together thirteen partners who have been chosen specifically for their expertise and experience to ensure the successful implementation of the novel research proposed in this project and to guarantee a widespread geographical coverage (Fig.1):

1. WIP – Renewable Energies (WIP), based in Germany, the project coordinator
2. ESTIA Institute of Technology (ESTIA), based in France, the scientific coordinator, with extensive experience in research aspect of social innovation and innovative business models for the energy sector
3. CARTIF, energy expert based in Spain
4. Bodensee-Stiftung - Lake Constance Foundation (LCF), based in Germany, as networking and innovation expert and providers of case studies for RES cooperatives
5. Adelphi, policy think tank based in Germany
6. Fondazione iCons (ICONS), communication, dissemination and exploitation expert based in Italy
7. Trinity College Dublin (TCD), University based in Ireland, with extensive experience in behavioural and energy economics, and consumer engagement
8. I-ENER, RES cooperative based in France, involved in social innovation research projects in the Aquitaine region.
9. EnergEtica, RES cooperative based in Spain
10. Power Parity, RES cooperative and crowdfunding platform based in Portugal
11. Abundance, RES crowdfunding platform based in United Kingdom
12. REGEA, RES crowdfunding platform based in Croatia
13. Tractebel, RES aggregator based in Romania

Figure 1: SocialRES geographical coverage

The research framing adopted for SocialRES is a pragmatic approach to research [2] focusing on the generation of actionable knowledge, i.e. knowledge that is helpful in solving pragmatic problems [3]. The SocialRES researchers' goal is not only to describe future sociotechnical systems, but also to understand the system by changing it.

The SocialRES consortium will follow an action research process to develop the case study approach. The action research process aims to generate knowledge while simultaneously trying to find solutions to problems [4]. In this project, researchers will focus not only on the development of novel business models and services, but also on their experimentation in the real world [5]. According to Van de Ven and Johnson [6], in this approach “researchers and practitioners co-produce knowledge that can advance theory and practice in a given domain”. The SocialRES approach will be implemented in four levels as shown in Figure 2:

1. Research
2. Innovation
3. Recommendations
4. Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation

Figure 2: SocialRES approach

Level 1. Research

Within this level, the SocialRES consortium will define the Status Quo of the implementation of social innovation in the renewable energy sector by focusing on the identification of the motivations driving social innovations among the European citizens who have decided to participate in renewable energies through cooperatives, crowdfunding or aggregators. This will be done by the comparative analysis of data related to the real-life implementation of the case studies provided by the SocialRES partners. The analysis is complemented by an investigation of behavioural aspects analysing smart meter data and with the support of two surveys (one a survey for citizens who are participating in energy cooperatives, aggregators and crowdfunding platforms and the second a survey with discrete choice experiments investigating future business models).

Level 2. Innovation

Cooperatives, crowdfunding platforms and aggregators are highly innovative and the driving forces for the energy transition in Europe. However, the activities of those actors are limited due to policy regulations, economical restrictions or the lack of professional support. The level of maturity of these organisations seems to be very different in the member states of the European Union and thus also in the participating partner's countries. We believe that bringing together all three forms of social innovation actors will create a new momentum and will offer new and highly innovative business cases. Presently, the three organisational forms coexist next to each other, each looking for new ways to develop themselves. Within SocialRES, we strive to form the scientific base for collaboration between them.

The newly developed business models can directly be cross-checked with practitioners in the field and adopted over the course of different mutual learning and networking activities. All of which coming to a climax in the project development hackathon towards the end of the project. The possible adaptation of the new business models will also be investigated for the partners of the SocialRES project and also for external stakeholders.

Level 3. Recommendations

The developed policy recommendations will help to structure the surroundings and the political framework accordingly to maximize the positive impact that social innovations can have in our society and for the energy transition in the EU. In order to support the advancements achieved during the SocialRES project in terms of social innovations in the energy sector, governments and authorities need to be able to assess their benefits properly. This includes:

- the distributional effects of support policies for social innovations;
- the degree to which they influence the security of supply of energy;
- the impact they have on local, regional and national economies;
- the impact they have on the price of energy
- the conditions under which they contribute to acceptance of change towards a low carbon energy supply.

This level will build on the analyses of these impacts over the course of the project. This will be achieved by scoping the need among Member States and devolved authorities for tools and guidance on policy process design, policy impact assessment and policy evaluation to measure and to optimise the value added by social innovations in the energy sector.

Level 4. Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation

The last level of the SocialRES project focuses on the activities needed to increase the awareness of all societal players (citizens, policy and decision makers, cooperatives, aggregators and crowdfunding platforms) and fostering uptake of its results. This will be done by generating and distributing contents addressing the general public, including citizens, public authorities, and stakeholders at large, with key, easy-to-understand and targeted messages focusing on the benefits deriving from knowledge exchange and outcomes from the research analysis on the importance of social innovation in the energy sector.

The activities to be carried out in this last phase of the project will focus on how partners intend to integrate SocialRES comparative analysis, recommendations, business models and other results in their strategy for the years to come. Depending on partners' missions, focus will be on research exploitation activities, the possibility to offer new services and/or adopt a new strategic approach to innovation. A particular attention will be given to partners of the case studies and their plans to make SocialRES a standard approach in supporting social ***innovation to clean energy transition.***

2 SCIENTIFIC INNOVATION AND RELEVANCE

The SocialRES innovation potential is based on devising more effective ways of increasing social innovation, leading to greater social acceptability as well as more durable governance arrangements and socioeconomic benefits. ***SocialRES considers the realisation of energy democracy as fundamental in the transition towards the Energy Union. Social innovations are the decisive tool in this transition as they give citizens the chance to become part of a community aimed at fostering energy democracy.*** Citizens clearly need to be researched more deeply and implemented in a broader context to become a real asset for the Energy Union.

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The innovative value of the SocialRES project is represented by the fact that crowd-funders, cooperatives and aggregators will define in the

project *new ways of cooperation leading to new business models and services of social innovations for the renewable energy sector*. Combining business models and services of those three organisations allows SocialRES to cover social (cooperatives), economic (crowdfunding) and technological (aggregator) aspects of the clean energy transition, whilst analysing related socioeconomic, gender, sociocultural, and socio-political issues. ***There are no European projects or initiatives aiming at combining all three aspects.***

SocialRES aims to comparatively analyse the success and contribution potential of the mentioned social innovations and to highlight their added value to a broad audience. The combination of the investigated social innovation schemes will result in their advancement and an increased level of cooperation. At the beginning of the project a comparative analysis, including behavioural aspects, will be performed to define the Status Quo on the implementation of social innovations for the renewable energy sector. The project will then identify the services required to create advancement over the existing situation by an evolution of the quality of interactions among citizens and cooperatives, crowdfunding platforms and aggregators. Afterwards the improvement in the cooperation among cooperatives, crowdfunding platforms and aggregators will expand the business models and services for social innovations to enhance the quality level in the energy market of the future. Thus, SocialRES realises project target for the empowerment of citizens in the renewable energy market of the future.

In details, the novel aspect of the SocialRES project beyond the state of the art is founded on the following two advancements.

Advancement 1: An increased cooperation within cooperatives, crowd-funders and aggregators with citizens, as well as among citizens

Based on the comparative and behavioural analysis, and thus the identified success potential of social innovations, SocialRES advances the state of the art by offering cooperatives, crowdfunding platforms and aggregators the necessary support services for their further, robust development in cooperation with the citizens in the centralised energy market of today. This is complemented by an enhanced cooperation among citizens.

Advancement 2: An increased cooperation between cooperatives, crowd-funders and aggregators

While the current business models and services imply certain restrictions to the interplay of various stakeholders, the SocialRES project will reach beyond the boundaries of existing business models and services by exploring new opportunities for cooperation between cooperatives, crowdfunding platforms and aggregators, which

leads to a comprehensive cooperation analysis. By exploring the cooperation potential of cooperatives, crowdfunding platforms and aggregators, their further development will be fuelled, whilst the cooperation between citizens is further cultivated; and both elements will be adjusted to the decentralised energy market of the future.

3 PRELIMINARY RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

During the expected duration of project activities, from May 2019 to ending in August 2022, SocialRES will develop socially innovative and inclusive strategies for the energy system of the future. SocialRES will supplement the existing fragmented data with new understandings from businesses, end-users and stakeholders to provide a comprehensive evidence base for policy design. The project will employ innovative techniques such as a Peer to Peer (P2P) crowd-investing for renewable energy sources (RES) projects, P2P lending and virtual PV electricity aggregator platform. Among the expected results, SocialRES will collect new data from 9 social innovation projects and 6,000 citizens across Europe, will develop new business and service models, define a vision for the future and will contribute to an extensive stakeholder and policy engagement.

4 REFERENCES

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